

ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF FABRIC-STRENGTHENED COMPOSITES CONSIDERING THREE-DIMENSIONAL CROSS-LINKED STRUCTURE

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Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) is widely used in the industrial fields because of its high specific modulus and strength. Out of these diversities, the attempt to estimate the deformational behaviour on FRP has been made. However, in most of those cases, the homogeneous anisotropic theory was applied from the macroscopic standpoint of, neglecting the heterogeneous characteristics of composites caused by the three dimensional non-homogeneous construction between cloth reinforcements and matrix.

In this paper, the structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics, considering the three dimensional cross-linked construction, is introduced for the purpose of grasping the mechanics on a FRP plate. And for the technical application, the problems on inter-lamina separation and stress concentration in FRP plate with a hole under the condition of uniaxial statical tensile load are analyzed by Finite Element Method (FEM) regarding the deformation as a finite elastic plastic problem.

The results obtained show that the analytical method considering the three dimensional heterogeneous construction between cloth reinforcements and matrix will give a good way for the practical design of cloth reinforced plastics to perform functions not possible with conventional materials.

1) Introduction

Cloth reinforced plastics, having the three dimensional heterogeneous construction composed by reinforcements with the weave structure and matrix, are widely used for the industrial purpose and its sphere field of utility is enlarging because of its superior mechanical characteristics. Accordingly the attempt has been made actively to estimate the mechanical behaviour of cloth strengthend composites. However, in most of those cases, the homogeneous anisotropic theory was applied from the macroscopic standpoint of, neglecting the non-homogeneous deformational behaviour of composites. The heterogeneous characteristics of these composites will be the key relation governing the mechanical behaviour of composites.

In the first part of this paper, the structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics consisting of truss and triangular elements is introduced to investigate the heterogeneous deformational behaviour of composites. Secondly, the comparison between the analytical and experimental results regarding the deformational behaviour of plane weave reinforced plastics under the uniaxial statical tensile load is discussed to capitalize on the sufficiency of the analytical method. The decreasing tendency on the stiffness which appears to be caused by the microscopic cracks in the weft yarn orthogonal to the load axis yield to the problem of material non-linearity. Also, the deformational behaviour of the composites is converted to the elastic plastic problem including material and geometrical non-linearities. Moreover, for the technical applications, such as inter-lamina separation and stress concentration in FRP plate with a hole under the uniaxial statical tensile load are analyzed by FEM in the final part.

2) Structural Model Unit and Fundamental Equations

Plane weave reinforced plastics is considered to be a three dimensional construction composed of cloth reinforcements having the plane weave structure and matrix. And this heterogeneous construction will mainly govern the mechanical characteristics of composites.

In this chapter, the idealized structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics is presented in order to estimate the response on behaviour of FRP plate. At the same time, the finite elastic plastic formulation leads to the equilibrium equation for the composites constructed by truss and triangular elements.

Fig. 1 Structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics

In Fig. 1, the idealized structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics composed by truss and triangular elements is shown. The truss and triangular elements on Y-Z plane possess the tensile rigidity of the warp yarn and the tensile or compressive rigidity of the fibre bundle of the weft yarn penetrated by the resin matrix orthogonal to the load axis, respectively. Such are the same for the truss and triangular elements on X-Z plane. Furthermore, the contractibility of the fibre bundle upon the tensile deformation of the yarn along its axis and the shearing resistance of the fascicle are taken into account with the triangular elements on the X-Y plane. In the case where approximating the lamina as combined structure of structural model unit, the following principle of virtual displacement can be applied for each constituent element at any equilibrium condition of⁽¹⁾

$$\int_V (\sigma_{ij} + \Delta\sigma_{ij}) \delta(\Delta E_{ij}) dV = \int_S (T_i + \Delta T_i) \delta(\Delta u_i) dS. \quad (1)$$

Separating the component of strain increment ΔE_{ij} into linear strain increment $\Delta \epsilon_{ij}$ and non-linear strain increment $\Delta \eta_{ij}$, and approximating the linear constitutive relation between stress increment $\Delta \sigma_{ij}$ and strain increment ΔE_{ij} (as shown in Eq. (2)), the Eq. (1) can be transposed as Eq. (3),

$$\Delta\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \Delta E_{kl}, \quad C_{ijkl} = C_{ijkl} (\bar{\sigma} \leq \sigma_Y), \quad C_{ijkl} = C'_{ijkl} (\bar{\sigma} > \sigma_Y), \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ denotes the equivalent stress and also σ_Y denotes the yielding stress.

$$\int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta(\Delta \eta_{ij}) dV + \int_V \Delta \epsilon_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta \epsilon_{ij}) dV + \int_V (\Delta \epsilon_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta \eta_{ij}) + \Delta \eta_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta \epsilon_{ij}) + \Delta \eta_{kl} C_{ijkl} \delta(\Delta \eta_{ij})) dV = \int_S \Delta T_i \delta(\Delta u_i) dS + (\int_S T_i \delta(\Delta u_i) dS - \int_V \sigma_{ij} \delta(\Delta \epsilon_{ij}) dV), \quad (3)$$

where

$$\Delta \epsilon_{ij} = (\Delta u_{i,j} + \Delta u_{j,i})/2, \quad \Delta \eta_{ij} = (\Delta u_{k,i} \Delta u_{k,j})/2. \quad (4)$$

Introducing Eq. (4) into Eq. (3) and expressing the increment of element displacement Δu_k by using the nodal value as shown in Eq. (5), the element equilibrium equation (6) can be given, where $k^{(e)}$ denotes the element stiffness matrix,

$$\Delta u_k = \phi_{ki} \Delta r_i, \quad (5)$$

$$[K_{Oij}^{(e)} + K_{Gij}^{(e)} + K_{Lij}^{(e)}] \cdot \Delta r_j = \Delta f_i, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} K_{Oij}^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{4} \int_V (\phi_{ki,1} + \phi_{li,k}) C_{klmn} (\phi_{mj,n} + \phi_{nj,m}) dV, \\ K_{Gij}^{(e)} &= \int_V \phi_{mi,k} \sigma_{kl} \phi_{mj,1} dV, \\ K_{Lij}^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{4} \int_V \{ (\phi_{ki,1} + \phi_{li,k}) C_{klmn} (\phi_{oj,m} \phi_{oj,n}) + (\phi_{oi,k} \phi_{oi,1}) C_{klmn} (\phi_{mj,n} + \phi_{nj,m}) \\ &\quad + (\phi_{oi,k} \phi_{oi,1}) C_{klmn} (\phi_{oj,m} \phi_{oj,n}) \} dV. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Accordingly, the stiffness matrix of combined structure constructed by idealized structural model unit can be given by adding the element stiffness matrix as follows;

$$\sum_{e=1}^E (e) K_{Oij} + \sum_{e=1}^E (e) K_{Gij} + \sum_{e=1}^E (e) K_{Lij} \cdot \sum_{e=1}^E \Delta r_j = \sum_{e=1}^E \Delta f_i . \quad (8)$$

3) Introduction of Material Properties

In this situation when approximating the lamina into combined structure composed of truss and triangular elements, the material and engineering constants of each constituent element can be given by the combined law of mixture⁽²⁾, in the case where the material constants of fibre and matrix, such as Young's modulus (E_f , E_m), Poisson's ratio (ν_f , ν_m) and the volume fraction of the fibre (V_f) are known. For example, the material properties of the truss elements or the triangular elements on X-Z or Y-Z plane can be determined as follows;

$$E_L = k\{E_f - (E_f - E_m)V_m\} , \quad V_m = 1 - V_f , \quad (9)$$

$$E_T = 2\{1-\nu_f + (\nu_f - \nu_m)V_m\} \left\{ (1-c) \frac{K_f(2K_m + G_m) - G_m(K_f - K_m)V_m}{(2K_m + G_m) + 2(K_f - K_m)V_m} + c \frac{K_f(2K_m + G_f) + G_f(K_m - K_f)V_m}{(2K_m + G_f) - 2(K_m - K_f)V_m} \right\} , \quad (10)$$

where suffix L and T represent the longitudinal or transverse direction, respectively, and the material constants k_f , k_m , G_f , and G_m are as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} K_f &= E_f/2(1-\nu_f) , & K_m &= E_m/2(1-\nu_m) , \\ G_f &= E_f/2(1+\nu_f) , & G_m &= E_m/2(1+\nu_m) . \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Such are the same for triangular elements on the X-Y plane. Here the material constants are shown in Eq. (12),

$$E_f = 68.6 \text{ GPa} , \quad E_m = 3.43 \text{ GPa} , \quad \nu_f = 0.22 , \quad \nu_m = 0.35 . \quad (12)$$

4) Numerical Research

While the macroscopic analysis can be viewed as a simple extension of conventional (homogeneous) materials, the microscopic analysis, however, must be viewed from a completely different viewpoint based on the heterogeneous materials for the FRP plate.

The advantage of the formulation by FEM for the structural model unit in this paper is similar to those for an enlarged view by a microscope. Therefore, the numerical results obtained by the model could lead to the microscopic view of the mechanical behaviour of FRP plate and make understood the unique behaviour of interlamina separation and stress concentration for technical application.

4-1) Investigation of the Structural Model Unit

The strip-shape plane weave reinforced plastics constructed by the structural model unit is shown in Fig. 2, where the specimen width is 20 mm. In this case the specimen length corresponds with its width, because the experimental results as slight effectiveness of specimen length on the mechanical behaviour of composites was obtained under the uniaxial statical tensile load⁽³⁾. The comparison between the numerical and experimental results of deformational behaviour on lamina under the uniaxial tensile load is discussed below, where the employed material constants are shown in Table 1 (volume fraction of fibre $V_f = 27\%$, coefficient of amendment $k=1$, $c=0.2$).

Also, the triangular elements on X-Y plane possess the yielding stress for shearing deformation $\sigma_Y/\sqrt{3}$ (σ_Y : yielding stress for tensile or compressive deformation) taking into account the characteristics of its element.

Table 1 Material properties of the constituent elements

	Young's Modulus E, GPa	Shearing Modulus G, GPa	Poisson's Ratio ν	Yielding Stress σ _Y , MPa	Hardening Ratio H', GPa
Triangular Element on X-Z or Y-Z Plane	26.6	10.2	0.3	67.6	4.5
Triangular Element on X-Y Plane	13.3	2.8	0.3	39.2	
Truss Element	21.0				

The stress-strain relationship obtained is shown in Fig. 3. At the same time the relation between the progress of plastic condition on constituent elements and the propagation of microscopic cracks in weft yarns are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Comparing the numerical results of stress condition developing to the elastic limit within the triangular elements on Y-Z plane with experimental results of the occurrence of microscopic cracks in the weft yarn, which is sometimes observed where the tensile strain is about 0.3%, it is considered that the stiffness drop on FRP plate is caused by the microscopic cracks produced in the weft yarn orthogonal to the load axis.

Fig. 2 Idealized strip-shape FRP plate

Fig. 3 Stress-strain relationship under the uniaxial static tensile load

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the heterogeneous deformational behaviour of composites, such as non-linear increment of the specimen thickness and the deformational behaviour of the weft yarn under the uniaxial static tensile load, respectively. In general, it is impossible to evaluate the non-linear increment of specimen thickness by the homogeneous anisotropic theory. However, despite its superior faculty of this structural model unit, the recovering from deformation of the weft yarn after the inter-lamina separation is inexplicable.

Considering the above results, the analytical method taking into account the three dimensional heterogeneous construction of composites composed of reinforcements having the weave structure and matrix will give a method for the practical structural unit on composites.

Fig. 4 Relation between the plastic condition on the triangular elements in Y-Z plane by FEM and microscopic cracks in the weft yarn by experiment

Fig. 5 Relation between the plastic condition on the triangular elements in X-Y plane by FEM and microscopic cracks in the weft yarn by experiment

Fig. 6 Non-linear increment of the specimen thickness by FEM

Fig. 7 Heterogeneous deformational behaviour in the left yarn by FEM

4-2) Inter-Lamina Separation on FRP Plate with a Hole

In this chapter, the progress of inter-lamina separation on FRP plate with a hole under the uniaxial statical tensile load is discussed for the first technical application of the analytical method.

In Fig. 8, the analytical model constructed by structural model unit is shown, where the ratio of hole diameter to specimen width is equal to 0.3. The stress-strain relationship obtained is shown in Fig. 9. Here, the material properties of the each constituent element are shown in Table 2 (volume fraction of fibre $V_f = 23.2\%$, coefficient of amendment $k=0.55$, $c=0.2$).

Fig. 8 Idealized FRP plate with a hole

Fig. 9 Stress-strain relationship under the uniaxial statical tensile load with a hole

Table 2 Material properties of the constituent elements

	Young's Modulus E, GPa	Shearing Modulus G, GPa	Poisson's Ratio ν	Yielding Stress σ _r , MPa	Hardening Ratio H', GPa
Triangular Element on X-Z or Y-Z Plane	11.0	4.2	0.3	100.9	3.7
Triangular Element on X-Y Plane	5.5	1.4	0.3	57.8	
Truss Element	9.3				

Comparing the analytical results of the increasing state of plastic condition on triangular elements in Y-Z or X-Y plane with the experimental results of the propagation of microscopic cracks and inter-lamina separation at any deformational condition after the knee (referred to Fig. 10), the comparative figure Fig. 11 to Fig. 13 can be obtained.

Concluding from the stress-strain relationship and the progress state of the plastic condition on triangular elements in Y-Z plane, the first stiffness drop which is observed at the stress-strain relationship is due to the occurrence of the microscopic cracks produced in the weft yarn. Also, the second stiffness drop where the stretch ratio is nearly equal to 1.1%, is due to the penetration of the plastic condition on triangular elements in Y-Z plane along the load axis, namely the propagation of microscopic cracks in the weft yarn to the load direction. And the occurrence of inter-lamina separation along the load axis at the deformational condition Step-1, is caused by the shearing deformation between the warp and weft yarns. Also, it is considered that the propagation of inter-lamina separation on FRP plate after the condition Step-2 is due to the penetration of microscopic cracks produced in the weft yarn into resin rich parts of the composites orthogonal to the load axis according to the tensile deformation of the warp yarn.

Concluding from the numerical results presented in this chapter, the occurrence of microscopic cracks and the progress of inter-lamina separation on FRP plate can be well explained by considering the three dimensional heterogeneous construction composed of cloth reinforcements and matrix.

Fig. 10 Correspondence of the deformational steps after the knee between numerical and experimental results

Fig. 11 Relation between the plastic condition on constituent elements by FEM and the propagation of microscopic cracks in the weft yarn by experiment at Step-1

Fig. 12 Relation between the plastic condition on constituent elements by FEM and the propagation of microscopic cracks in the weft yarn by experiment at Step-2

Fig. 13 Relation between the plastic condition on constituent elements by FEM and the propagation of microscopic cracks in the weft yarn by experiment at Step-3

4-3) Stress Concentration on FRP Plate with a Hole

In this chapter, as the second application of the analytical method presented in this paper, the numerical results of stress concentration on FRP plate (both specimen length and width are equal to 80 mm) with a hole during the process of uniaxial static tensile load is discussed. In those cases, the numerical research is performed under the deformational condition of the knee considering the fact that in spite of the great influence of the heterogeneous behaviour of constituents on FRP plate with a hole, the recovering from deformation of the weft yarn after the inter-lamina separation cannot be well explained by this model. Also, the analysis is performed both radical boring types considering that the deformational behavior of the composites will be affected by the boring type of a hole. Namely, the strain distribution on FRP plate will be different in both cases, where the hole center exists between the neighboring fibre bundle (as shown in Fig. 14, Type-A) and on the crossing section of the fibre bundle (as shown in Fig. 14, Type-B).

Fig. 14 Illustration of radical boring types of a hole

Consequently, in the first part of this chapter the relationship between the analytical and experimental results on the tangential stress distribution around the hole is shown, where the ratio of hole diameter to specimen width ρ/B is equal to 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15. Secondly, the tangential stress distribution around the hole, the range of tensile stress at the minimum cross section of the FRP plate and the transition of maximum stress concentration factor governed by the hole diameter are presented, where ρ/B is equal to 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20. In those cases, as shown in Fig. 15, the heterogeneous displacements are put into the homogeneous anisotropic plate considering the impossibility of evaluating the sudden stress transition near the hole by the analytical model. Here the material properties of the constituents are the same as shown in Table 1, and in experimental analysis, the theory of photoelasticity was applied.⁽⁴⁾

Fig. 15 Illustration of the numerical method to put into the heterogeneous displacement into the homogeneous anisotropic plate

Fig. 16 Example of the FEM mesh division on heterogeneous FRP plate with a hole ($\rho/B=0.10$, Type-B)

Fig. 17 Example of the FEM mesh division on homogeneous anisotropic plate with a hole ($\rho/B=0.10$)

Fig. 18 Relation between the analytical and experimental results of tangential stress distribution around a hole

Fig. 19 Effect of amendment factor k to the maximum stress concentration factor α_{max}

In Fig. 16 and Fig. 17, examples of FEM mesh division are shown where the heterogeneous plate is constructed by a structural model unit and a homogeneous anisotropic plate. Here the ratio of hole diameter to specimen width ρ/B is equal to 0.1 and the boring type belongs to Type-B. In Fig. 18, the relation between the analytical and experimental results of tangential stress distribution around a hole is shown, where the employed amendment factor k (referred to Eq. (9)) for homogeneous anisotropic plate is equal to 0.6 taking into account the examined analytical results as shown in Fig. 19. In these cases, symbols σ_0 and α_{max} denote the average tensile stress at the minimum cross section on FRP plate and the maximum stress concentration factor (the ratio of maximum tangential stress around a hole to average stress σ_0). As shown in Fig. 18, there is good agreement between numerical results and experimental results.

Continuing, the effect of heterogeneous construction on deformational behaviour in FRP plate with a hole is analyzed where the hole diameter and boring type differs. In Fig. 20 and Fig. 21, the analytical results of tangential stress distribution around a hole and the range of tensile stress at the minimum cross section on FRP plate are

Fig. 20 Distribution of the tangential stress around a hole and tensile stress at the minimum cross section of the FRP plate with a hole (Type-A)

Fig. 21 Distribution of the tangential stress around a hole and tensile stress at the minimum cross section of the FRP plate with a hole (Type-B)

Fig. 22 Distribution of the tangential stress around a hole and tensile stress at the minimum cross section of the FRP plate with a hole (homogeneous)

shown. At the same time for the purpose of comparing with above results, the results obtained by homogeneous anisotropic theory are also shown in Fig. 22.

Concluding from these results, it is considered that the maximum tangential stress on FRP plate exists the minimum cross section of the plate; however, the transition of its stress is not uniform compared to the homogeneous plate. Also it is observed that the tensile stress to the side of minimum cross section does not decrease. It will suggest that the contractive deformation on FRP plate with a hole against the uniaxial tensile deformation is restricted by the existence of the weft yarn orthogonal to the load axis.

From these results the relation between the maximum stress concentration factor α_{max} with the ratio of hole diameter to specimen width ρ/B , which is shown in Fig.23, can be obtained. This result also shows not only the effect of a hole diameter but also the boring type on the deformational behaviour of FRP plate with a hole.

In this chapter, as discussed above, the condition of stress distribution in FRP plate with a hole is investigated in both radical boring types (Type-A and Type-B). Only in practice where the boring type does not belong to both types or the irregular laminate, the maximum stress concentration factor should be varied within the oblique range which is shown in Fig. 23.

Fig. 23 Relation between the maximum stress concentration factor α_{max} and the ratio of hole diameter to specimen width ρ/B

5) Conclusion

Despite the high utility of cloth reinforced plastics, their design depends mainly upon homogeneous anisotropic theory. And in most of those cases the three dimensional heterogeneous construction by reinforcements and matrix are neglected.

In this paper the structural model unit of plane weave reinforced plastics constructed by truss and triangular elements is introduced for the purpose to evaluate the mechanics of composites. And the deformational behaviour of FRP plate with a hole, such as inter-lamina separation and stress concentration under the uniaxial statical tensile load are analyzed by FEM regarding the deformation as a finite elastic plastic problem including material and geometrical non-linearities.

In view of these factors, the analytical method considering the three dimensional cross-linked construction of composites will give an available way for the practical design of cloth strengthend composites.

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7) References

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